

Research papers

Uncertainty in nitrate load calculations evaluated using Monte Carlo simulations based on in-situ nitrate sensors in two Danish headwater streams

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ABSTRACT

This study used high-frequency (HF) nitrate-nitrogen (NO₃-N) sensor data to explore the uncertainty of calculating NO₃-N loads in two headwater streams (Horndrup and Lyby-Grønning) with infrequent sample collection. Accurate annual and monthly N load estimates are crucial for cost-efficient management of N in catchments and for correct calibration and validation of catchment models like SWAT. Ultraviolet (UV) NO₃-N sensors were installed in the two agricultural headwater streams for two hydrological years (June 2021 to May 2023) to measure NO₃-N concentrations every minute. The cleaned dataset was used to investigate NO₃-N load estimates using a Monte Carlo approach, with 1000 simulations for five infrequent sampling strategies: daily, weekly, fortnightly, 18 annual samples, and monthly samples. Bias (Flux Bias Statistic), precision (standard deviation), and total uncertainty (RMSE) were calculated for the annual and monthly NO₃-N loads. Richards-Baker Flashiness Index (RBI) was used to explore the influence of hydrology on differences between HF and infrequent sampling. The sampling strategy needed to meet a bias and achieve RMSE <2 %, 5 %, and 10 % for monthly loads was explored.

The uncertainty of the load estimates increased with fewer grab samples. The bias and RMSE of the annual load estimates from the five strategies were <±7.7 % and <10.3 %, respectively. Monthly NO₃-N loads had higher uncertainties, with average bias and RMSE of ±4 % and 15 % (max. -13 % and 28 %) in Horndrup Stream and ±7 % and 27 % (max. 89 % and 194 %) in Lyby-Grønning Stream. In Horndrup Stream, a significant negative linear relationship between the bias of monthly NO₃-N loads and RBI indicated higher underestimation with more storm events. In Lyby-Grønning Stream, precision decreased with higher RBI.

1. Introduction

Excess nutrient losses from agricultural areas can lead to eutrophication in freshwater and coastal marine waters, degrading their ecological quality (Schindler et al., 2008; Breitburg et al., 2018). Eutrophication is a global concern and poses significant challenges, especially in Europe and North America (European Environment Agency et al., 2018; Jones et al., 2018; Petersen et al., 2021; The European Commission, 2021). Despite implementation of action plans to reduce nutrient loads, high amounts of nutrients, especially nitrogen (N), still occur, lowering the ecological quality of coastal waters (European Environment Agency et al., 2018; HELCOM, 2018; Jones et al., 2018; The European Commission, 2021). In addition to lowering the ecological

quality of water, nitrogen (specifically nitrate) is also a threat to human health when present in high concentrations in drinking water (Appelo and Postma, 2004).

Agricultural runoff is a primary source of stream N loads (Mitsch et al., 2001; Wit et al., 2020; Petersen et al., 2021). Nitrogen concentrations and loads tend to increase during rain events, though with varying intensity depending on the size of storm events, baseflows, seasons, and catchment areas (Bierzoza et al., 2014; Jones et al., 2018). This implies that the traditional infrequent grab sampling strategy used in monitoring programs struggles to capture these dynamics, leading to uncertainties in monthly and annual N load estimates (European Environment Agency and Nixon, 1996; Rozemeijer et al., 2010; Kulasova et al., 2012; Burkitt et al., 2017). Reliable N load estimates are essential

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for water quality modelling, policy development, and cost-efficient implementation of mitigation measures (Rode and Suhr, 2007; Hoffmann et al., 2020). Most monitoring programs calculate N loads from manual grab samples taken with a frequency of 4 to 26 samples per year (European Environment Agency and Nixon, 1996; Kulasova et al., 2012; Williams et al., 2015).

While some authors have investigated the importance of using NO₃-N sensors for annual N-load estimates compared to infrequent sampling strategies, there are still limited studies on smaller headwater catchments (Williams et al., 2015). Headwater streams play a critical role in downstream nutrient transport and water quality management, and yet few studies have assessed sampling uncertainties in these systems, especially at monthly resolution (Alexander, et al., 2007). Investigating the uncertainty of monthly NO₃-N load estimates is crucial for several reasons. First, understanding when N loads reach downstream recipients, such as lakes and coastal waters, is essential. These ecosystems often exhibit immediate biological responses, particularly when they have short water residence times (Josefson and Rasmussen, 2000). Therefore, accurate and unbiased N load estimates are crucial for the ecological quality in, for example, several Danish coastal waters and lakes during late spring and summer to ensure accurate River Basin Management Plans (Erichsen et al., 2024). As countries such as Denmark move toward implementing N regulations based on seasons (Erichsen et al., 2017), the need for accurate monthly load estimates becomes even more critical to support effective policy and management decisions. Second, accurate monthly N load estimates are already important to national monitoring programs to support the requirements of the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) (The European Commission, 2021). They support dynamic physical models and empirical models, which are used to simulate catchment responses under varying climatic, hydrological, and agricultural conditions (Højberg et al., 2015b; Erichsen et al., 2017). These models help identify N thresholds for streams and downstream ecosystems, informing national regulatory frameworks (Josefson and Rasmussen, 2000; Højberg et al., 2015a; Vervloet et al., 2018). Knowledge of the uncertainty of data used for calibration and validation of models such as the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) catchment Model (Arnold et al., 1998) and the Hydrological Predictions for the Environment (HYPE) model (Lindström et al., 2010) is therefore a great advantage for modellers (Han et al., 2023; Oates et al., 2024). Together, these points underscore the significance of this study and its contribution to investigating the accuracy and applicability of monthly N load assessments in environmental management.

Studies have examined the uncertainty of annual N loads using intensive grab sampling relative to different strategies. Kronvang and Bruhn, (1996) found that monthly sampling underestimated total N (TN) loads by up to 8 % RMSE compared to hourly data (Bruhn and Kronvang, 1990; Kronvang and Bruhn, 1996). Williams et al. (2015) showed that infrequent sampling underestimated annual nitrate-N (NO₃-N) loads by -11 % to -14 %, recommending sampling every 2.7 to 17.5 days to keep uncertainty below ±10 % (Williams et al., 2015). Birgand et al. (2011) found that weekly sampling resulted in bias up to -28 % and RMSE up to 19 %, while monthly sampling led to bias as high as -57 %, with RMSE up to 36 %, in two streams (Birgand et al., 2011).

The implementation of in-situ sensors for measuring nutrient concentrations in streams has allowed high-resolution investigations and more accurate nutrient load estimates (Rode et al., 2016). While nitrogen exists in various forms, this study focuses on nitrate because it is the only major form of nitrogen that can be routinely measured using in-situ sensors. Moreover, in agricultural streams, nitrate typically constitutes the major part of total nitrogen. In Danish streams, nitrate accounts for between 80 % to 90 % of total nitrogen (Petersen et al., 2021). Recent studies using HF NO₃-N sensors have demonstrated improved load estimates compared to grab sampling. For example, Burkitt et al. (2017) and Wade et al. (2012) showed that monthly sampling underestimated annual loads by up to -14 % and 36 %, respectively, in New Zealand and

England. Wade et al. (2012) also found that daily sampling led to bias of up to 0.7 %, while weekly and fortnightly sampling yielded an overestimation of annual NO₃-N-load of up to 18 %. Bieroza et al. (2014) also found that sampling frequency has a high impact on the accurate measurement of N concentrations and loads. They found similar biases in monthly load estimates in UK streams with underestimations of up to -33.7 % for monthly estimates and up to -30.1 % for loads for four months in total. This highlights the limitations of infrequent monitoring.

Furthermore, although HF sensors have become more common in research and monitoring networks, and large international sensor networks already exist in both USA and Australia (Dekker and Hestir, 2012; van Geer et al., 2016; Chabbi and Loescher, 2017; Edmonds et al., 2022; Bieroza et al., 2023), their use in national programs remains limited (Fölster et al., 2019; Kaste et al., 2023; Skarbovik et al., 2023). Exceptions include Ireland and the UK, where HF sensor measurement of water quality has been integrated into agricultural catchment programs (Jordan et al., 2012; Hawkins, Griffith and Harris, 2023).

This study aimed to establish time series of high-frequency minute-resolution NO₃-N concentrations from two Danish agricultural headwater streams. Using this unique dataset, we conducted Monte Carlo simulations to evaluate the bias, precision, and total uncertainty (RMSE) when calculating annual and monthly NO₃-N loads of five infrequent sampling strategies, normally used in national monitoring programs. We also explored how stream hydrology, characterized by the Richards-Baker Flashiness Index (RBI), influences uncertainty in load estimates.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study sites

Two Danish headwater streams draining arable catchments were chosen as study sites. The Horndrup Stream drains a catchment area of 5.48 km² in the eastern part of Jutland, Denmark, and Lyby-Grønning Stream drains a catchment area of 11.3 km² in the northern part of Jutland, Denmark. Both headwater streams drain a moraine landscape from the latest glaciation period (Weichel). The catchment area of Horndrup Stream consists of 70 % agricultural land and 19 % forest (Levin et al., 2017). The soils are primarily dominated by moraine deposits: fine sand mixed with clay (59 %) and fine clay mixed with sand (27 %). The catchment area to Lyby-Grønning Stream is dominantly agricultural land (84 %) (Levin et al., 2017). The soils are dominated by fine sand mixed with clay (47 %) and fine clay mixed with sand (52 %). Both stream stations are included in Denmark's national program for monitoring of the aquatic environment (NOVANA) (Windolf et al., 2012; Petersen et al., 2021). Annual precipitation for the Horndrup catchment was 793 mm (June 2021 to May 2022) and 862 mm (June 2022 to May 2023); for the Lyby-Grønning catchment, annual precipitation was 787 mm (June 2021 to May 2022) and 916 mm (June 2022 to May 2023) (Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut, 2024a). For comparison, the average annual precipitation in Denmark from 2011 to 2022 was 787 mm/year (Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut, 2024b). See Appendix A for a figure showing the study sites.

2.2. In-situ sensor nitrate measurement

NO₃-N sensors of the type NITRATAX plus ultraviolet (UV) photometrical sensors (HACH, Düsseldorf, Germany) were installed in-situ in both streams during two hydrological years (June 1, 2021 to May 31, 2022 & June 1, 2022 to May 31, 2023). In the Nordic context, the hydrological year is defined as the period from June 1st to May 31st, reflecting the annual runoff including the seasonal cycle of snow accumulation and melt (Det Danske Hedeselskabs Hydrometriske Undersøgelser, 1978).

The two sensors gathered data continuously for the two years with 1-minute frequency. The sensors have a measurement range between 0.1 and 100.0 mg N/L and a precision/uncertainty of 3 % or ±0.5 mg N/L

(HACH, 2012, 2014). The sensors were manually cleaned with hydrochloric acid (HCL) 5 % in the field every two weeks from June 1, 2021 to January 1, 2023 in both streams and every month in Horndrup Stream and every second month in Lyby-Grønning Stream from January 1, 2023 to May 31, 2023. The decision to change the manual cleaning frequency from fortnightly to monthly and every second month was based on our observation that the less frequent cleaning interval was sufficient to maintain sensor accuracy.

The sensor data was processed following the five steps outlined in (van't Veen et al., 2024). Focus in steps 1 and 2 was on the setup of sensors, establishing a database, and maintaining an electronic logbook. In step 3, sensor data were corrected for zero offsets, which occurred linearly over time in the two streams and were stream- and season-specific (Appendix B). This was investigated using an automatic ISCO grab sampler, which took grab samples at fixed intervals for NO₃-N analysis in the laboratory, following the procedure described in (van't Veen et al., 2023) and compared with sensor measurements. A daily grab sample was collected using the automatic ISCO sampler over 24 days, referred to as a monitoring campaign. This campaign was repeated in different seasons throughout the year to analyse the zero offsets in the streams. However, in Horndrup Stream, only a minimal linear zero offset was observed during the summer (Appendix b, Table b1). Thus, sensor measurements were corrected using measurements before and after manual cleaning, and by verifying the sensor readings in distilled, demineralized, and purified water in the field after the manual cleaning. The raw sensor measurement was corrected following equation (1):

$$\text{corr}C_{\text{NO}_3\text{-N}} = C_{\text{NO}_3\text{-N}} - \frac{C_{\text{dif}}}{N_{\text{total}}} * N_i \quad (1)$$

where:

$\text{corr}C_{\text{NO}_3\text{-N}}$: corrected NO₃-N sensor measurement.

$C_{\text{NO}_3\text{-N}}$: raw NO₃-N measurement.

C_{dif} : sensor measurement before manual cleaning of the sensor – sensor measurement after manual cleaning of the sensor.

N_{total} : number of data points from the last manual cleaning of the NO₃-N sensor in the field to the next cleaning.

N_i : number of data point since last manual cleaning to actual measurement.

In step 4, quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) were performed using the Python program SentemQC (Andersen et al., 2024) on the sensor measurements after zero-offset calibration. SentemQC is a method that ensures the quality of sensor data by conducting QA and QC on large volumes of high-frequency (HF) sensor data (van't Veen et al., 2024).

After performing QA-QC using SentemQC on the sensor data, the identified anomalies were masked. Subsequently, the sensor data was cleaned using the electronic logbook, masking out all known incorrect data points, such as those identified during manual field cleaning or when the sensor was in the lab for calibration. The final datasets from Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream were gap-filled using linear interpolation. For Horndrup Stream, 7.1 % of the dataset was gap-filled, with SentemQC marking out 3.7 %. In Horndrup, the longest data gaps were typically approximately one hour during manual cleaning of the sensor. For the Lyby-Grønning Stream dataset, 12.7 % was gap-filled, with SentemQC marking out 0.1 %. The 12.7 % in Lyby-Grønning was primarily due to a software update problem with the sensor probe at the beginning of the monitoring period in June and July 2021, as well as issues with the sensor's connection to the database from January to February 2023, which resulted in several days of missing data. Consequently, much of the data from these four months in the final Lyby-Grønning dataset was gap-filled using linear interpolation. This introduces uncertainty as changes in N concentrations are missed, for example, during storm events. Therefore, the results from these four months in Lyby-Grønning Stream are shaded in Figs. 8 and 10b. Output files from SentemQC are in Appendix C, and a figure illustrating the

cleaned sensor NO₃-N data, the zero-offset corrected data, and the raw sensor data is in Appendix C.

2.3. Discharge

Discharge data at 5 and 10-minute intervals were available from NOVANA for the gauging stations in Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream for the two-year monitoring period. The discharge was calculated based on an established water level (H)-discharge (Q)-relationship (Q/H) for each stream station. However, for Horndrup Stream Doppler sensor measurements were used instead of stage-discharge (Q-H) relationships in 2023 (Ovesen and Poulsen, 2017). In Horndrup Stream, water level (H) was measured using a pressure transducer every 5 min from June 2021 to June 2022, and every 15 min from June 2022 to June 2023. In Lyby-Grønning Stream, water level was measured every 5 min from June 2021 to April 2022 and every 10 min from April 2022 to June 2023. In both streams, instantaneous measurements of discharge (Q) were conducted 18 times per year (fortnightly during the winter period) with an Ott MF Pro Instrument using the NOVANA technical guideline (Ovesen, 2011; Ovesen and Poulsen, 2016; van't Veen et al., 2023; Miljøministeriet, 2024).

For Horndrup Stream Doppler measurement from January 2023 to May 2023, six days of missing discharge data (three days in March and 3 days in May) were gap-filled using linear interpolation and calculated daily average discharge data.

2.4. Runoff, precipitation, and Richards-Baker flash index

The daily discharge data for Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream were used to calculate daily, monthly, and annual runoff for their catchments. Danish Metrological Institute (DMI) provided daily corrected precipitation with a grid size of 10X10 km² for Horndrup Stream (grid 10,285 (20074)) and for Lyby-Grønning Stream (grid 10,136 (20039) and 10,135 (20038)) for the two monitoring years (Danmarks Metrologiske Institut, 2024a). Runoff was calculated as the sum of discharge for a given period, for example, monthly, divided by the catchment area.

The Richards-Baker Flashiness Index (RBI) measures how quickly and dramatically discharge changes over time (Baker et al., 2004). A higher RBI indicates more frequent and large fluctuations in discharge, making the stream flashy. The RBI is dimensionless and unaffected by flow measurement units (Baker et al., 2004). The RBI was calculated for every month during the two-year measuring period using daily discharge values at the Horndrup and Lyby-Grønning Streams (Baker et al., 2004).

$$\text{RBI} = \frac{\sum |Q_i - Q_{i-1}|}{\sum Q_i} \quad (2)$$

where:

RBI: Richards-Baker Flashiness Index (dimensionless).

Q_i : discharge on day i.

Q_{i-1} : discharge the previous day.

2.5. Monte Carlo N-load approach

2.5.1. Calculation of the "true" NO₃-N load

The instantaneous NO₃-N load for Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream was calculated using minute values for concentrations and discharge over the two measurement years. This load is referred to as 'the true load' in this study, as it is the most accurate load estimate available. The true load calculations were based on cleaned, QA-QC corrected, and gap-filled using linear interpolation minute values of NO₃-N concentrations and discharge (Kronvang and Bruhn, 1996; Bøgestrand and Erfurt, 2014; van't Veen et al., 2018). The 1-minute discharge data was obtained by linearly interpolating the 5, 10, and

15-minute discharge data described in Section 2.3. Nitrogen loss was calculated by the sum of NO₃-N load divided by the catchment area.

The “true” load was calculated as follows (Equation (3)):

$$L_{\text{true}} = \sum_i 60 * c(t_i) * q(t_i) \quad (3)$$

where the summation is for every minute in a given period, e.g. month or year.

- L_{true} : true load (kg).
- c : NO₃-N concentration (mg N/L).
- q : discharge (L/s).
- t time (1 min separation).

2.5.2. Monte Carlo simulations

A Monte Carlo (MC) approach (Davison and Hinkley, 1997) was applied to the 1-minute NO₃-N sensor concentration and discharge data for Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream over the two measurement years, on both an annual and monthly basis. Five different MC sampling strategies, based on those applied in NOVANA, were selected to investigate the uncertainty of infrequent sampling. The strategies included daily, weekly, fortnightly, 18 annual samples (monthly in summer (April-September) and fortnightly in winter (October-March)), and monthly (Table 1). For the 1000 MC simulations, daily mean discharge and linearly interpolated daily NO₃-N concentrations were used for each strategy. This approach was chosen because it aligns with the NOVANA program methodology (Bøgestrand and Erfurt, 2014).

The different strategies were applied in the MC simulation. For simplicity, we describe the MC process using a monthly sampling frequency, though this description applies to all sampling frequencies simulated in this study. With NO₃-N concentrations at 1-minute intervals, we have a total of 40,320, 43,200, or 44,640 concentrations each month to randomly choose from when performing MC. Each month, a concentration was randomly chosen according to a discrete uniform distribution, giving each concentration an equal probability of being selected. For the monthly sampling strategy, one sample was randomly chosen each month, resulting in a total of 12 concentrations for each monitoring year. This means that the random sampling strategy was restricted to selecting one sample per month. These 12 concentrations were then expanded to 365 daily concentrations by linear interpolation, and an annual load was calculated using equation (4):

$$L_{\text{MC}} = \sum_{i=1}^{365} c(t_i) * \bar{q}_i * 86400 \quad (4)$$

where:

- L_{MC} : Monte Carlo simulation load (kg).
- c : daily NO₃-N concentration (mgN/L).
- \bar{q} : daily mean discharge (l/s/day).
- t : time (daily time steps).

In the 1000 MC load simulations, sampling concentrations within each strategy were chosen completely randomly, without enforcing equidistant sampling. For example, in the daily sampling strategy, samples were randomly chosen within each day. This random approach is more accurate for investigating uncertainty compared to a controlled strategy (Cochran, 1977) as it provides a better theoretical basis for examining load uncertainties. Furthermore, in our MC approach, we

tested an example where we fixed the sampling to an equivalent weekly interval strategy and found no significant difference in the results. Additionally, for the shorter periods where linear interpolation was used for gap-filling in the NO₃-N concentration datasets, data points have more decimal places, resulting in ‘closer’ values due to increased precision. Rounding can introduce noise (measurement uncertainty). Therefore, we did not round the linearly interpolated data points to maintain precision.

2.5.3. Bias, precision, and total uncertainty (RMSE) of the Monte Carlo simulations

As described above, 1000 MC simulations were run for each sampling strategy, where j denotes each MC simulation, $j = 1, 2, \dots, 1000$, and d_j the difference between the MC load and the true load (Equation (5)):

$$d_j = L_{\text{MC}j} - L_{\text{true}}, j = 1, 2, \dots, 1000 \quad (5)$$

Statistical parameters were calculated from the 1000 load simulations for each station and sampling strategy for annual and monthly loads. These parameters include the mean, standard deviation, maximum load, minimum load, and median. The deviation from the true load (%) was calculated for the parameters using equation (6):

$$\text{Deviation from the True Load}(\%) = \frac{d_j}{L_{\text{true}}} * 100 \quad (6)$$

To investigate the uncertainty of the annual and monthly nitrogen loads, the Flux Bias Statistic (bias), precision, and total uncertainty were calculated. The Flux Bias Statistic (bias) represents the difference between the simulated loads and the true load and was calculated based on the definition of the Flux Bias Statistic (Hirsch and De Cicco, 2015), including a minor alteration as we divided by the true load rather than the estimated load in the calculations. A positive bias indicates overestimation, while a negative bias indicates underestimation. Precision represents the standard deviation and, therefore, the variability of the simulated loads around their mean. The equations for calculating bias, precision, and total uncertainty are (Equations (7) to (12))

$$\text{Bias (kg)} = \frac{1}{1000} \sum_{j=1}^{1000} d_j \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Precision (kg)} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{1000} \sum_{j=1}^{1000} (L_{\text{MC}j} - \bar{L})^2} \quad (8)$$

where:

\bar{L} : $\frac{1}{1000} \sum_{j=1}^{1000} \text{MC}_j$; the mean of the 1000 MC simulations (kg).

$L_{\text{MC}j}$: Monte Carlo simulation (kg).

Because relative numbers are useful when comparing different streams bias (%) and precision (%) were calculated based on equations (9) and (10) (Hirsch and De Cicco, 2015).

$$\text{Bias (\%)} = \frac{\text{Bias (kg)}}{\text{True Load (kg)}} * 100 \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Precision (\%)} = \frac{\text{Precision (kg)}}{\text{True Load (kg)}} * 100 \quad (10)$$

Table 1

Overview of the different load calculation sampling strategies at the two study sites Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream in the two hydrological years June 1, 2021 to May 31, 2022 and June 1, 2022 to May 31, 2023.

	True load	Monte Carlo sampling strategy – based on true load dataset				
		Load 1	Load 2	Load 3	Load 4	Load 5
Sampling strategy	All 1-minute measurements after QA-QC, calibration etc.	Daily	Weekly	Fortnightly	18 annual samples (fortnightly in winter months and monthly in summer months)	Monthly
Number of samples per year	1,051,920	365	52	24	18	12

Total uncertainty (RMSE) represents the combined uncertainty of bias and precision. See equations (11) and (12):

$$\text{Total uncertainty (kg)} = \sqrt{\text{Bias}^2 + \text{Precision}^2} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Total uncertainty (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total uncertainty (kg)}}{\text{True load (kg)}} * 100 \quad (12)$$

3. Results

3.1. Stream hydrology

The average discharge for Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream followed the same pattern for the two studied hydrological years June 2021 to May 2022 and June 2022 to May 2023, with the highest discharge from December to February and the lowest from June to September (Fig. 1). In Horndrup Stream, the average discharge was higher than the 30-year average from 1991 to 2020 in 6 out of 12 months during the first monitoring year in (Fig. 1), and in 3 months in the second monitoring year (Fig. 1). For Lyby-Grønning Stream, the average discharge was generally low compared to the 30-year average during the first monitoring year in 8 out of 12 months during the first year, and low in the first 6 months of the second year (Fig. 1). Especially in January in the second year, discharge was very high for both streams (Fig. 1).

3.2. NO₃-N sensor measurements

The cleaned NO₃-N sensor measurements from June 2021 to July 2023 are generally higher in Lyby-Grønning Stream (maximum 16 mg N/L) than Horndrup Stream (maximum 6 mg N/L) (Fig. 2). In Horndrup Stream, the NO₃-N concentrations correlate with the discharge data, with high NO₃-N levels during winter and fall when discharge was also high (Fig. 2). The NO₃-N sensor data enables exploration of NO₃-N concentration behavior in the catchment during heavy rain events (Fig. 3). In Horndrup Stream, NO₃-N concentrations increased during storm events in all seasons (Fig. 3). However, compared to the discharge response, a delay in NO₃-N peaks occurred, depending on season and storm event intensity (Fig. 2). Diurnal discharge and NO₃-N concentration variations occurred in April 2021 and from May to September 2022, with NO₃-N concentrations peaking at night discharge at its lowest in the early morning and peaking during the day (Fig. 3a, 3b).

In Lyby-Grønning Stream, the NO₃-N concentrations did not follow the discharge data as in Horndrup Stream, which would not have been discovered without HF sensor data. Instead, NO₃-N concentrations decreased in the early phase of storm events when discharged increased during the rising limb of the hydrograph (Fig. 4), indicating dilution of the stream water with water containing lower amounts of NO₃-N during

rain events. However, in June 2021, a heavy rain event produced a small decrease in NO₃-N concentrations, followed by a large increase, from ca. 4 mg N/L to 16 mg N/L (Fig. 4b). On June 6 and July 25, 2021, smaller rain events decreased the NO₃-N concentration (Fig. 4b).

High NO₃-N peaks were observed without a corresponding increase in discharge over short periods (hours) in the Lyby-Grønning Stream (Fig. 4). These peaks were only detected due to the HF sensor dataset and would have been missed using the infrequent grab sampling strategy typically employed. These sporadic high NO₃-N peaks appeared throughout the two-year monitoring period (Fig. 2b and 4).

3.3. True load

The 'true' annual NO₃-N load calculated from QA-QC 1-minute sensor measurements for Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream is shown in Table 2 for both years. The annual NO₃-N loss is nearly the same in both years and catchments (Table 2). For Horndrup Stream, the highest annual NO₃-N load occurred in the second monitoring year, which also had the highest precipitation and runoff (Table 2). In contrast, for Lyby-Grønning Stream, the NO₃-N load was highest in the first monitoring year, despite lower annual precipitation and runoff compared to the second monitoring year (Table 2). The lowest NO₃-N load was in the second monitoring year in Lyby-Grønning Stream, although it had the highest annual precipitation and runoff (Table 2).

The monthly runoff is higher in Horndrup Stream than in Lyby-Grønning Stream (Fig. 5b). Monthly runoff is highest during winter (January-February) and lowest during summer (June-August) (Fig. 5b). In both years, 'true' NO₃-N loads for both streams were highest in winter months (December-March) and lowest in summer (May-September) (Fig. 5a).

3.4. Monte Carlo load simulations

3.4.1. Uncertainty in annual NO₃-N load estimations

The results of the 1000 Monte Carlo (MC) simulations of annual average bias, precision (standard deviation), and maximum and minimum deviation from the 'true' annual NO₃-N load for the five different grab sampling strategies are shown in Fig. 6, while the total uncertainty (RMSE) together with the other uncertainty metrics are seen in Table 3. A table with the corresponding annual results in kgs of N is found in Appendix E, Table E1, for reference. The bias and RMSE of the N load estimates increased when the number of grab samples included in the sampling strategy decreased. The N load estimate calculated using the fewest number of samples (monthly sampling strategy) showed the highest bias and RMSE in both years in the two streams (Table 3). However, the precision of the load estimations became lower when the sampling interval was large, which also indicated a lower accuracy of the load estimates using fewer samples in the sampling strategy (Fig. 6

Fig. 1. Monthly average discharge calculated from 30 years (1991 to 2020) and monthly average discharge for the two hydrological monitoring years included in this study (2021 to 2022 and 2022 to 2023) for Horndrup Stream (a) and Lyby-Grønning Stream (b).

Fig. 2. Nitrate (NO₃-N) sensor and discharge data from June 1, 2021 to May 31, 2023, in a) Horndrup Stream and b) Lyby-Grønning Stream.

Fig. 3. Monthly sensor measurements examples of nitrate (NO₃-N) concentrations and discharge in Horndrup Stream.

and Table 3).

Horndrup Stream generally had the lowest total uncertainty of the N load estimations for all sampling strategies and a negative bias, and the annual load estimates were thus underestimated (Fig. 6). In both streams, the lowest bias and precision occurred in the second year (Fig. 6). The average bias for the five strategies was 0.7 % to -1.9 % in Horndrup Stream in the first and -0.2 % to -7.7 % in the second year

(Fig. 6). Therefore, the annual NO₃-N load was measured with high precision in the first year but showed increasing underestimation in the second year as sampling frequency decreased.

The precision (standard deviation) measured, equaling a 68 % confidence interval, ranged from -21.4 % to 6.0 % in the second year, compared to -12.2 % to 8.9 % in the first year for the monthly strategy in Horndrup Stream. As expected, the lowest percentage deviations were

Fig. 4. Monthly sensor measurements examples of nitrate ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) concentrations and discharge in Lyby-Grønning Stream.

Table 2

True annual transport and loss of nitrate-nitrogen, runoff, and precipitation in Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream in two monitoring years.

Study site	Hydrological year	True annual load (kg N/year)	Loss (kg N/ha)	Runoff (mm/year)	Precipitation (mm/year)
Horndrup Stream	2021–22	5228	9.5	311	793
	2022–23	5482	10.0	313	862
Lyby-Grønning Stream	2021–22	11,714	10.4	133	787
	2022–23	11,559	10.2	179	916

found for the daily grab strategy, all below $\pm 2.6\%$ (Fig. 6). In Lyby-Grønning Stream, the bias for the annual $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ MC simulations was very low ($< 1\%$) and positive for all five grab sampling strategies for both years (Fig. 6). The precision ranged from -7.1% to 7.2% in the first year, compared to -5.9% to 5.8% in the second year for the monthly sampling strategy. Horndrup Stream's total uncertainty (RMSE) was larger in the second monitoring year for all sampling strategies except the daily, ranging from 0.69% to 10.30% , compared to the first year's range from 0.9% to 5.5% . For Lyby-Grønning Stream, the opposite occurred, with the highest RMSE in the first year, ranging from 0.65% to 8.0% , compared to 0.50% to 6.2% in second year 2 (Table 3).

3.4.2. Uncertainty of monthly load calculations

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the results of the Monte Carlo (MC) approach for monthly average percentage bias, precision (standard deviation), and total uncertainty (RMSE) from the 'true' monthly $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ load for the five different grab sampling strategies. A table with the corresponding monthly results in kg of N is found in Appendix E, Tables E2 and E3 for reference. The MC simulations indicate that monthly bias and precision have significantly higher uncertainties compared to annual $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ loadings in both streams (Figs. 7 and 8). Similar to the annual simulation, the N load estimation accuracy increased with fewer grab samples, making the monthly grab sampling strategy have the highest

uncertainties for all three statistical parameters in both streams (Figs. 7 and 8). The bias was negative for 18 out of 24 months in Horndrup Stream for all strategies except daily sampling when simulating monthly $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ loads (Fig. 7a). In six of the months, the bias exceeded -10% (Fig. 7a). In Lyby-Grønning Stream, the MC-simulated monthly $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ load was generally overestimated (13 out of the 24 months), and in five months, the $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ load was overestimated by more than 10% (Fig. 8a). The monthly load was especially overestimated during summer (June to August 2022), by up to 89% (Fig. 8a). Underestimation occurred in 9 out of the 24 months; however, bias exceeded -10% only in October 2022, and in 7 months bias did not exceed -5% (Fig. 8a).

In Horndrup Stream, precision (standard deviation) of the monthly $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ -load was higher than 10% for 17 out of the 24 months for most sampling strategies (Fig. 7b). The highest values of precision occurred in September and October in both monitoring years; however, all strategies, except daily, also had very low precision in April 2022 (high values of precision) (Fig. 7b). In Lyby-Grønning Stream, precision was above 10% for most strategies (Fig. 8b). Again, September and October had low precision in both monitoring years in Lyby-Grønning Stream (Fig. 8b).

In Horndrup Stream, the total uncertainty (RMSE) exceeded 10% in 12 of the 24 months, peaking above 15% in August, September, and October of both monitoring years (Fig. 7c). For Lyby-Grønning Stream, the total uncertainty of N load estimations was above 10% in 8 of the 24 months (Fig. 8c), with peaks above 15% in August and September (Fig. 8c). Notably, in June, July, and August 2022, the total uncertainty of the N load estimations in Lyby-Grønning Stream rose to 194% . In September 2022 and May 2023, total uncertainty was also high, up to 60% (Fig. 8c). Conversely, very low uncertainty (under 5%) was observed in October and December 2022 and January to March 2023 for all strategies in Lyby-Grønning Stream (Fig. 8c).

3.5. Analysis of hydrological factors

The Richards-Baker Flashiness Index (RBI) was used to determine if the strength of storm events, as indicated by hydrological data, could

Fig. 5. (a) True monthly nitrate (NO₃-N) load for Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream calculated from 1-minute NO₃-N sensor data and discharge data from June 2021 to May 2023. (b) Monthly runoff for Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream from June 2021 to May 2023.

explain the uncertainties in monthly NO₃-N loads from the MC simulations. Stronger rain events will result in flashier stream conditions (i.e., higher RBI values). The average monthly bias and precisions for the 1000 MC simulations of the N load estimated based on the monthly sampling strategy for each stream over the two-year monitoring period were compared to the RBI in Fig. 9. We used the monthly grab sample strategy because it is a common grab sampling frequency in monitoring programs (European Environment Agency and Nixon, 1996; Williams et al., 2015; Burkitt et al., 2017).

We found that the RBI explained part of the bias and precision (std) of the MC monthly simulations (Fig. 9 and Appendix F). In Horndrup Stream, a significant ($P = 0.005$) negative linear relationship between bias and RBI appeared in the two monitoring years ($R^2 = 0.30$) (Fig. 9A) while a poor relationship was found between precision and RBI ($R^2 = 0.02$) (Fig. 9B). In Lyby-Grønning Stream, a significant ($P < 0.001$) linear relationship was found between precision (std) and RBI for both monitoring years ($R^2 = 0.67$) (Fig. 9D) while a poor relationship was found between bias and RBI ($R^2 = 0.03$) (Fig. 9C).

3.6. Number of grab samples to obtain monthly NO₃-N loads bias below 2, 5, and 10 %

Fig. 10 and Appendix G show the number of grab samples required to achieve a monthly NO₃-N load bias below 10 %, 5 %, and 2 %. As was expected, the number of monthly grab samples increases rapidly when the bias for the monthly NO₃-N load is reduced from <10 % to <2 % (Fig. 10).

In Horndrup Stream, daily grab sampling was required in September and October 2022 to obtain a bias <10 % (Fig. 10a). Reducing the monthly NO₃-N-load bias to <5 % required daily grab sampling in 8 out

of 24 months, and 14 months of daily sampling was required to achieve a bias of <2 % (Fig. 10a). In Lyby-Grønning, daily sampling in June and August 2022 was insufficient to achieve a bias of <10 %. To obtain a bias below 5 %, daily sampling was required in 5 out of the 24 months, and daily sampling was needed in 9 out of the 24 months to achieve a bias <2 %, (Fig. 10b).

4. Discussion

4.1. Experience with use of high-frequency nitrate sensor measurements

In this study, we used high-frequency (HF) in-situ NO₃-N sensor measurements to simulate loads and investigate the uncertainty associated with various grab sampling strategies applied in national monitoring programs. All sensor data underwent a five-step quality assured and quality controlled (QA-QC) process (section 2.2) (van't Veen et al., 2024), including zero-offset correction using measurements before and after manual field cleaning and SentemQC (Andersen et al., 2024).

Unlike van der Grift et al. (2016), who corrected for sensor drift in their Nitratex sensor measurements using grab samples, we decided not to use grab sample concentrations for correction. This decision was based on documented uncertainties in grab sampling, which was found for grab sample NO₃-N concentrations up to 0.05 mg N/L (Lin et al., 2023), including systematic errors (biases) up to 18.1 %, and standard deviations up to 3.3 % (American Public Health Association et al., 1998; Rode and Suhr, 2007). Therefore, we decided to use sensor measurements taken before and after manual cleaning, supplemented with demineralized (DI) water controls of the sensors to correct for zero offsets.

After zero offset calibration, our QC cleaned sensor data showed

Fig. 6. 1000 Monte Carlo simulations showing bias (mean), median, precision (standard deviation), and maximum/minimum percent deviation from the true load for the five different sampling strategies for two years (from June 1, 2021 to May 31, 2022 and from June 1, 2022 to May 31, 2023) in Horndrup Stream: a) first year, b) second year and Lyby-Grønning Stream: c) first year, d) second year.

Table 3

Annual percent deviation from true load for bias, precision (standard deviation), and total uncertainty (RMSE) from Monte Carlo simulation of N load in the two headwater streams Horndrup and Lyby-Grønning in two monitoring years (June 1, 2021 to May 31, 2022 and June 1, 2022 to May 31, 2023).

Sampling strategy	Number of samples per year	Monitoring year	Horndrup Stream – Annual load			Lyby-Grønning Stream – Annual load		
			Precision (%)	Bias (%)	Total uncertainty RMSE (%)	Precision (%)	Bias (%)	Total uncertainty RMSE (%)
Daily	365	Year 1	0.7	0.7	0.9	0.6	0.3	0.7
Daily	365	Year 2	0.7	-0.2	0.7	0.4	0.2	0.5
Weekly	52	Year 1	2.3	0.2	2.3	1.9	0.3	2.0
Weekly	52	Year 2	2.1	-2.3	3.1	1.0	0.3	1.0
Fortnightly	24	Year 1	3.5	-0.3	3.5	2.9	0.3	6.6
Fortnightly	24	Year 2	3.4	-3.9	5.1	1.8	0.1	3.9
18 annual samples	18	Year 1	3.6	-0.4	3.6	2.7	0.4	6.2
18 annual samples	18	Year 2	4.2	-4.5	6.2	2.1	0.1	4.4
Monthly	12	Year 1	5.3	-1.6	5.5	3.6	0.1	8.0
Monthly	12	Year 2	6.9	-7.7	10.3	2.9	-0.1	6.2

strong agreement with grab samples (R^2 values of 0.95 for Horndrup Stream and 0.97 for Lyby-Grønning Stream (Appendix H)), indicating high reliability. This supports the use of HF sensor measurements as an alternative to traditional grab sampling for nitrate monitoring.

4.2. Causes of differences between sensor and grab sampling load estimates

4.2.1. Uncertainty of annual load estimates

The uncertainty of estimating annual $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ load increased as sampling frequency decreased, with monthly sampling showing the

highest uncertainties (Fig. 6 and Table 3). This aligns with previous findings of Kronvang and Bruhn (1996), and Williams et al. (2015).

In this study, monthly sampling underestimated annual loads by -1.6% to -7.7% in Horndrup Stream and remained within $\pm 1\%$ in Lyby-Grønning Stream. These biases were lower than those reported in other catchments, such as the -14% underestimation found by Burkitt et al. (2017) in the large catchment of Manawatu River (3.913 km^2) in New Zealand using in-situ optical nitrate sensor measurements. Wade et al. (2012) also observed variable biases (2% to -36%) depending on sampling day in a UK stream with a catchment area of 148 km^2 .

The bias between infrequent grab sampling and annual true $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$

Fig. 7. Horndrup Stream: Monthly bias from June 2021 to May 2023 (a), precision (standard deviation) (b), and monthly total uncertainty (RMSE) (c) using the Monte Carlo approach.

load differed between the two streams. Horndrup Stream showed in general negative (underestimation), likely due to missed storm-driven NO₃-N peaks, while Lyby-Grønning Stream in general showed slight positive (overestimation), possibly due to dilution effects during high flow events and consistently high NO₃-N groundwater inputs due to either surface runoff or another flow component (Shrestha et al., 2013) (Fig. 6 and Table 3). Similar to several other studies, such as Wade et al. (2012) and Bieroza et al. (2014), we expected an increase in stream NO₃-N concentrations during storm events due to leaching and relatively quick transport of NO₃-N from fields to streams via, for instance, tile drains. Infrequent grab sampling does not always capture such NO₃-N dynamics during storm events and thus gives a negative bias such as found in Horndrup Stream.

Uncertainty of the annual load estimates also varied by year. In Lyby-Grønning Stream, the highest uncertainties occurred during the drier

second monitoring year, while in Horndrup, it was highest during the wetter first year (Table 3). These patterns reflect the influence of hydrological variability on NO₃-N loads and sampling representativeness and are similar to the results of (Kronvang and Bruhn, 1996) investigating the uncertainty of annual TN load estimates in two Danish agricultural headwater streams.

4.2.2. The dynamics of nitrate concentrations in the two streams

In both streams, NO₃-N concentrations and loads were generally highest during fall and winter and lowest during summer (Figs. 2 and 5), reflecting seasonal precipitation and the fact that agricultural fields may leach high amounts of NO₃-N after harvesting the main crop due to excess rainfall increasing root zone percolation (Børgesen et al., 2022). NO₃-N concentrations in both streams were dynamic during short-term storm events, with quite different responses (Fig. 2a and 2b). As

Fig. 8. Lyby-Grønning Stream: Monthly bias from June 2021 to May 2023 (a), precision (standard deviation) (b), and monthly total uncertainty (RMSE) (c) using the Monte Carlo approach.

described, short-term storm events caused rapid and variable $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ responses, which infrequent grab sampling often failed to capture. This aligns with findings from Wade et al. (2012) and Bieroza et al. (2018), who emphasized the influence of hydrological and land-use factors on $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ dynamics. Hashemi et al. (2020) and Bieroza et al. (2018) studied various hysteresis concentration-discharge (C-Q) relationships in streams using both HF sensor monitoring and intensive grab sampling to understand the N behavior in the catchments. Their analysis showed that C-Q slope analysis combined with HF monitoring is useful for evaluating water quality management actions.

Diurnal $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ concentration dynamics were also observed in spring and summer, especially in Horndrup Stream, with nighttime peaks (03.00 to 05.00) and afternoon lows (around 17.00) (Fig. 3a, 3b, and 4b). These diurnal variations are likely due to high daytime biological uptake. Wade et al. (2012) also reported daily variations in $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$

concentrations in a UK stream, which were particularly pronounced during low-flow periods in spring and summer. In some periods, they even observed a two-peak diurnal phase of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, which may be due to sewage discharges to the stream in the catchment. No major point sources are found in our two catchments, but daily discharge variations were periodically noted (with a maximum around 14.00 and a minimum around 06.00, see Fig. 3a). The diurnal discharge fluctuations during spring and summer may be explained by evapotranspiration as they strongly correlate with water temperature fluctuations.

In Lyby-Grønning Stream, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ concentrations often decreased during rain events (Fig. 2), suggesting dilution by surface runoff and macropore water from tile drains, both low in $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ (Grant et al., 1996). Another plausible explanation is that the upper sandy-gravel groundwater aquifer in the catchment area contains high legacy $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ concentrations from former agricultural nitrate leaching. As limited

Fig. 9. Average monthly bias calculated from 1000 Monte Carlo annual load simulations using a monthly sampling strategy including one sample every month versus Richards-Baker Flashiness Index (RBI) from June 1, 2021 to May 31, 2023 in Horndrup Stream a) and Lyby-Gronning Stream c). Average monthly precision (standard deviation) calculated from 1000 Monte Carlo annual load simulations and monthly grab samplings versus Richards-Baker Flashiness Index (RBI) from June 1, 2021 to May 31, 2023 in Horndrup Stream b) and Lyby-Gronning Stream d).

Fig. 10. The number of grab samples required to achieve monthly load biases of <10 %, <5%, and <2 % for a) Horndrup Stream and b) Lyby-Gronning stream from June 2021 to May 2023 calculated from 1000 Monte Carlo (MC) simulations the NO₃-N loads in the two streams.

denitrification takes place in this aquifer due to low organic carbon content, groundwater borehole logging from the Danish National Groundwater Monitoring (GRUMO) has measured NO₃-N in groundwater up to 13.6 mg N/L (Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland, 2024). Therefore, water leaching from fields during storm events today delivers new water through tile drains having lower NO₃-N concentrations than the high NO₃-N legacy water infiltrating from groundwater aquifers in the catchment area. Wade et al. (2012) also found significant dilution of NO₃-N in a UK stream during high flow events caused by groundwater discharge with a high NO₃-N content.

Additionally, in Lyby-Grønning Stream, we also observed sporadic short NO₃-N peaks not correlated to discharge (Fig. 4), possibly linked to farm outlets in the catchment or groundwater upwelling from small spring areas (Hill, 1996; Steiness et al., 2021).

4.2.3. Monthly load estimates uncertainty

Few international studies investigate monthly uncertainties of infrequent sampling frequencies for estimating NO₃-N loads. This study found that the uncertainty when estimating monthly loads using infrequent sampling was much higher than when estimating annual loads (Figs. 7 and 8). In Horndrup Stream, the monthly bias and RMSE ranged from -13 % to 5 % and 5 % to 28 %, respectively. In Lyby-Grønning Stream, they ranged from -22 % to 89 % and 0.2 % to 194 % respectively, when conducting a monthly grab sampling strategy (Figs. 7 and 8). These results are consistent with Bierozza et al. (2014) and Kronvang and Bruhn (1996), who also reported higher uncertainties during low-flow summer months, however, in these summer months, the loads (kg) were low (Fig. 5). Bierozza et al. (2014) found underestimations of -22.7 % and -33.7 % in April and May, and biases of -13.2 % and 18.8 % in August and September, respectively. These results are similar to most monthly loads in Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream, with an average bias and RMSE of ±4 % and 15 % in Horndrup Stream and ±7 % and 27 % in Lyby-Grønning Stream.

Notably, January 2023, Lyby-Grønning Stream had the lowest uncertainty (bias and RMSE <1 %). However, this was due to problems with connection to the sensor database and data loss, implying that the data is gap-filled with linear interpolation. Therefore, the results for this month are highly uncertain and marked in Fig. 8, like other months with large periods of missing data.

These findings highlight the challenge of using infrequent grab sampling to estimate monthly loads. This has important implications for calibrating and validating catchment models like SWAT (Arnold et al., 1998) and HYPE (Lindström et al., 2010) as the models are only as good as the input data, as pointed out by several modelers (Xu et al., 2016; Oates et al., 2024). Oates et al. (2024) argue that models are very important for filling observational gaps, but they cannot completely replace monitoring, which is problematic in the USA. Using HF sensor data to obtain more accurate load estimates can improve catchment models, aiding in assessing nutrient pressures and implementing catchment management plans with cost-efficient dosing of mitigation measures.

RBI was used to explore the influence of hydrology on the differences between HF sensor measurements and infrequent sampling (monthly). We found that RBI explained at least part of the uncertainty (Fig. 9 and Appendix F). The negative correlation between bias and RBI in Horndrup Stream (Fig. 9A) indicates that more storm events cause higher underestimation of the monthly NO₃-N loads. In contrast, in Lyby-Grønning Stream, more storm events (higher RBI) resulted in lower precision of the monthly load estimates (Fig. 9b, Appendix F). These differences are due to the differences between the two streams (Section 3.2).

Seasonal correlations are likely seasonally dependent, with fall (September to November) showing the highest number and intensity of rain events (highest RBI), ranging from 0.20 to 0.31 in Horndrup Stream and 0.25 to 0.57 in Lyby-Grønning Stream. During this period, the highest correlation to the RBI was found for bias, precision (SD), and

RMSE (total uncertainty) for both streams (Appendix F). In this study, NO₃-N constitutes an average of 79 % and 92 % of total nitrogen (TN) in Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream for the monitoring period, calculated based on data obtained from the Danish national surface water database ODA (Aarhus University, 2025). This suggests similar underestimation trends for TN as observed for NO₃-N in the investigated streams. However, since TN includes multiple nitrogen fractions beyond NO₃-N, it cannot reliably serve as a proxy, an assumption not evaluated in this study. Uncertainties remain particularly for organic nitrogen, which comprises both dissolved organic nitrogen (DON) and particulate organic nitrogen (PON) forms. Accurate TN quantification likely requires further development, including the use of turbidity sensors (as a proxy for PON), dissolved organic carbon (DOC) sensors (for DON), and ammonium sensors. Given the complexity of measuring each fraction individually, direct TN measurement may be more feasible. For example, HACH (Düsseldorf, Germany) offers TN analyzers suitable for stream deployment (HACH, 2021), however, this requires a more complex setup in the stream.

4.3. Optimal grab sampling frequencies in headwater streams

Determining the optimal grab sampling frequency in headwater streams is challenging and depends on the specific monitoring objectives (Bruhn and Kronvang, 1990). The key question is how much uncertainty we are willing to accept in the NO₃-N load estimates relative to the costs. While HF sensor data are more costly, they offer improved accuracy and deeper insights into NO₃-N dynamics, potentially justifying the investment.

A previous study suggests that to achieve annual NO₃-N load uncertainties below ±10 %, sampling every 5.5 to 17.5 days may suffice (Williams et al. 2015). Birgand et al. (2011) investigated the measurement required to obtain uncertainty levels of ±2 %, ±5%, and ±10 % for annual NO₃-N loads. They found that a sampling frequency of 17 h is needed for ±2 %, 37 h for ±5 %, and 43 h for ±10 %, for mixed-use catchments. They also investigated a forested catchment where fewer samples were needed: 45 h, 3.8 days, and 7 days, respectively (Birgand et al., 2011). In our study, 18 annual samples were needed in Horndrup Stream to achieve a ±10 % bias and <10 % RMSE for annual load estimates over the two monitoring years, while monthly samples were sufficient for Lyby-Grønning Stream. For higher accuracy (±5% or ±2 % bias and RMSE), weekly or daily sampling is needed for both streams (Table 3, Appendix G).

However, even daily sampling did not always achieve <10 % uncertainty for estimating monthly loads, especially in summer months in Lyby-Grønning Stream (Fig. 8). However, the actual summer load (in kg) was low (Fig. 5a). This suggests that achieving <5 % or <2 % uncertainties for monthly load estimates may require more than daily sampling in our two headwaters agricultural catchments.

We calculated the cost of the number of grab samples needed each month for the two headwater streams, aiming for monthly biases below 10 %, 5 %, and 2 % for NO₃-N loads (Appendix I, Table I2). A bias above +10 % for example, there would be a high risk of over-implementation of mitigation measures in the catchment, wasting money. On the other hand, a bias below -10 % would risk an insufficient number of mitigation measures being implemented in the catchment, which comes with a cost for harming the environment (e.g. vulnerable recipients such as coastal waters and lakes).

The cost analysis showed that annual HF sensor monitoring, costing around 12 K€/year (Appendix I, Table I1) could be more cost-effective than grab sampling because the cost is comparable to and actually lower than collecting grab samples with biases <5 % and <2 % from the "true" monthly loads (Appendix I). For example, achieving <5 % monthly bias with grab samples would cost 26 to 27 K€/year in Horndrup Stream and 16 to 22 K€/year in Lyby-Grønning Stream (Appendix I). Reducing grab sampling to 4 to 6 times per year could offset sensor costs while maintaining acceptable accuracy.

Fig. 10 illustrates the number of grab samples needed to meet different uncertainty thresholds (biases below $\pm 10\%$, 5% , and 2% for monthly loads). While our analysis focused on fixed sampling frequencies (monthly, fortnightly, weekly, and daily), it is important to note that the optimal number of required samples likely lies between the weekly and daily frequencies (i.e., 4 to 30 samples per month). This is a limitation as our study did not capture the full range of potential sampling frequencies.

5. Conclusion

This study used a Monte Carlo (MC) approach with high-frequency (HF) sensor measurements to assess the uncertainty in nitrate-nitrogen (NO₃-N) load estimates from two small Danish headwater streams over two hydrological years. Five grab sampling strategies (number of samples per year) were simulated (daily, weekly, fortnightly, 18 annual samples, and monthly samples), to evaluate bias, precision, and total uncertainty (RMSE) in annual and monthly load estimates.

Generally, the uncertainty in annual and monthly N load estimates increased as the number of annual samples decreased. For the two monitoring years, the bias and RMSE in annual NO₃-N load estimates from the five grab sampling strategies were $<\pm 7.7\%$ and $<10.3\%$, respectively, in Horndrup Stream and Lyby-Grønning Stream.

Monthly load estimates showed significantly higher uncertainty compared to annual estimates, with biases ranging from -13% to 5% and RMSE from 5% to 28% in Horndrup Stream, and biases from -22% to 89% and RMSE from 0.2% to 194% in Lyby-Grønning Stream.

The dynamics of NO₃-N concentrations varied between the two streams. While Lyby-Grønning Stream is highly affected by groundwater-surface water interaction with groundwater infiltrating the stream with high legacy NO₃-N concentrations, Horndrup Stream is more dominated by NO₃-N from present conditions in the catchment. This difference influences the bias and precision of the nitrate load estimates from HF sensor monitoring. The Richards-Baker Flashiness Index (RBI) showed a significant negative linear relationship between bias of monthly NO₃-N load and monthly RBI in Horndrup Stream, and a significant linear relationship between the precision of the NO₃-N load and RBI was found in Lyby-Grønning Stream.

Surprisingly, we only found a few studies that have investigated the uncertainties related to monthly N-loads based on infrequent grab sampling despite its common use in national monitoring programs. The findings from this study highlight the importance of sampling frequency and hydrological factors in accurately estimating monthly and annual nitrate loads in small headwater streams, which is crucial for effective catchment management.

6. Statement

During the preparation of this work, the authors used the Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) tool Microsoft Copilot to proofread and improve the language of the text. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content, as needed, and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sofie G.M. van't Veen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Søren Erik Larsen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Peter Mejlhede Andersen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software. **Niels Bering Ovesen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Data curation. **Jane Rosenstand Laugesen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Brian Kronvang:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding

acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2025.133816>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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